
**Socio-Economic Status of Ainwadi Village in Shahuwadi Tahsil of
Kolhapur District (Maharashtra): A Case Study**

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Abstract:

Socio-economic status is an important aspect of study at local, national and global level. Socio-economic status of society gives a clue to understand the socio-economic background of the villagers. Socio-economic status in rural areas is gradually improving over a period of time. Different types of economic as well as social classes are found in a village.

For the present study primary data has been collected from 71 families (63.00 percent) out of 113 families inhabiting in Ainwadi Village. Socio-economic condition depends primarily on occupations, education, income and wealth. The entire primary data collected by the researchers through proper questionnaire. The present research work highlights on systematic study of socio-economic status of peoples from hilly part of Ainwadi village in Shahuwadi tahsil.

Keywords: Annual Income, Occupational Structure, Educational Level, Socio-Economic Status.

Introduction:

In rural areas in India, now days due to increased per capita income and use and application of modern agricultural practices and tools the socio-economic status of peoples is consistently improving. Literate peoples and farmers in villages are apt to use new technology in their occupation. According to Dutton and Levine (1989), Socio-Economic status is “a composite measure that typically incorporates economic status measured by income, social status measured by education and work status measured by occupation”.

To understand socio-economic status of peoples, important indicators primarily occupational structure, annual income and educational status of sample families are taken into consideration for the present study. Other indicators constitutes cropping pattern, use of seeds and fertilizers, type of

farming and source of water are also highlighted. Way of life of peoples depends upon their socio-economic condition. Hence the study of ‘Socio-Economic Status of Ainwadi Peoples’ is selected for the research work. All these indicators are studied respectively and results are shown and depicted through tables, diagrams, proper analysis and discussion.

Study Area:

Socio-economic status of peoples in western hilly region of Kolhapur district gives an indication to understand of social and economic background of peoples and rural development in the study area. Study area selected for the present research work is “Ainwadi Village” which is located in hilly tracts of Sahyadri Mountain in Shahuwadi tahsil of Kolhapur district in Maharashtra, India. There are 140 villages in Shahuwadi

tahsil. The village Ainwadi is situated 14 km away from Malkapur and 55 km away

from district headquarter, Kolhapur.

Ainwadi village lies on 16^o50'36.6" North Latitude and 73^o52'20.9" East Longitude. The total geographical area of Ainwadi village is 692 hectare (6.92 sq.km.). Total Population of Ainwadi village is 665, consisting 335 male and 330 female. There are 113 families in Ainwadi village. The researchers have randomly selected 71 families consisting 516 working population.

The simple statistical method and represented with suitable cartographic techniques such as bar graph and pie-chart.

Objectives:

The main objectives of the present study are as follows:

1. To analyze occupational structure of peoples in Ainwadi village.
2. To study annual income and educational status of sample families.
3. To study agricultural practices of sample families/farmers.

Result And Discussion:

In the month of February 2024, researchers have taken a Survey of 71 families in Ainwadi village of Shahuwadi tahsil in Kolhapur District.

Table-1 Ainwadi: Occupational Structure

Sr. No.	Occupation	Number	Percentage
1	Farmers	376	72.87
2	Own Business	42	8.14
3	Service Sector	27	5.23
4	Unemployed	71	13.76
Total		516	100.00

Source: Field Survey, Feb-2024

Fig. 1

Database And Methodology:

The present research work is based on primary data which is collected through questionnaire and keen observations. Random sampling technique is used for the present study. There are total 113 families in Ainwadi village, out of which 71 families are selected as a sample size. These 71 families comprise 516 members as working population. The collected data analyzed with

Occupational structure is a significant indicator of economic status of individuals as well as of the society. It is observed that, 73 percent peoples are

engaged in farming sector, 8 percent peoples have their own business and 5 percent peoples are engaged in service sector whereas 14 percent peoples are unemployed in sample study. Table 1 and Figure 1 indicate that farming is a major economic

activity in the village. Own business comprises grocery, kerosene, automobile, auto rickshaw, Poultry farming etc. Proportion of unemployment is high due to the lack of higher education facilities.

Table-2: Ainwadi: Annual Income of Sample Families

Income (in Rs)	No. of Family	Percentage
Up to 10,000/-	05	7.04
10,001-20,000/-	09	12.68
20,001-30,000/-	29	40.85
30,001-40,000/-	08	11.27
40,001-50,000/-	08	11.27
More than 50,000/-	12	16.90
Total	71	100.000

Source: Field Survey, Feb-2024

Fig.2

Table 2 and Fig 2 shows annual income of sample families. It is found that, 19.72 percent families have their annual income up to 20,000/- rupees, 52.12 percent families income ranges between 20,001/- to 40,000/- rupees and 28.16 percent families annual income is more than 40,000/- rupees. These statistics clearly indicates that the numbers of middle class families are high in Ainwadi Village.

Table-3: Ainwadi: Educational Status

Sr. No.	Educational Status	Number	Percentage
1	Illiterate	159	30.81
2	Primary	248	48.06
3	Secondary	51	9.88
4	Higher Secondary	15	2.91
5	Graduates	43	8.33
Total		516	100

Source: Field Survey, Feb-2024

At the time of field survey, the researchers observed that there is only a primary school in the village. The students for their secondary, higher secondary and UG education goes to Malkapur, which is adjacent higher educational place whereas for their PG education students goes to Kolhapur, which is a district place having

State University. It is also found that 69 percent peoples are literate and 31 percent peoples are illiterate. This means that the proportion of illiterate people is much more than the average (20 percent) of India.

While surveying socio-economic status of Ainwadi, researchers have observed that the proportion of dry farming (54

percent) is higher than that of irrigated farming (28 percent) and fallow land (18 percent). All families depends on natural source of water i.e. rainwater and spring for their agricultural practices. However it is important to note here that five farmers have their wells, one family have their own borewell and one farmer have prepared a separate tank for irrigation. While considering use and application of seeds and fertilizers in agriculture, 50 percent families insisted on traditional seeds and manure. Farmers uses high yielding varieties (HYVs) and chemical fertilizers in order to increase per hectares production of a particular crop, wherever artificial sources of water are made available. The researchers have found that rice crop (95 percent) dominated the cropping pattern in Ainwadi village. Other important crop includes nachani and vari. It is also found that majority families are engaged in rearing cows and buffaloes for dairy production.

Conclusion:

As Ainwadi village is located in Western Ghat, rugged topography is observed throughout the study area. Tropical dry deciduous forests are common. Red soil is common whereas black soil is found in patches.

The above study provides glimpses of socio-economic profile of sample families in Ainwadi village and ascertains their socio-economic status. The numbers of middle class families are high (52.12 percent) as compared to other classes i.e. high income & low income. As far as sex ratio is concerned there are 335 males and 330 females are inhabitants in this village. As far as occupational structure is concerned the proportion (72.87 percent) of farmers is at apex than other occupation. Generally the proportion of illiterate peoples (30.81 percent) is high.

Researchers have observed that there is a lack of higher education system, transportation and medical facilities as well as apathy of people's representatives towards local problems. The study suggests that there is need of government assistance to promote the participation of farmers in agricultural training and workshop and to avail the higher educational facilities in Ainwadi village. There is an urgent need to construct district level roads, so that the communication with neighboring towns and cities will be possible.

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